

SECTION 2.

ENGINEERING

ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT LANGUAGE COURSES FOR E-LEARNING

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Modern approaches to the study of foreign languages are developing, gaining various options and methods in offline learning (language courses, Tutors, self-helpers), and in the online environment (online courses, video courses, mobile applications). Informatization and active introduction of mobile devices, as well as the ubiquitous availability of the Internet and content for every taste, lead to the fact that the attention and interest of the user become only less over the years. Thus, according to a study by the Harvard Business School, the user compared with the early 2000s began to pay less attention to advertising, including targeted advertising, since most often it is either untimely or irrelevant [1]. The reason for this change is the increase in the amount of information noise, which does not allow people to concentrate and immerse themselves deeply in some material or action. This also indicates the lack of interest of the younger generation in the deep study of educational material, which argues that it is now possible to find the necessary information at any time and study it in a "couple of clicks". Accordingly, there is a similar popular opinion regarding foreign languages, formed primarily by the ubiquitous availability of online translators, which in some cases allows you to have a virtually live conversation with a native speaker.

To solve the problem of students' involvement in the educational process through the means of digitization, it is necessary to study the material by them following the criteria that are decisive in the field of education in the classical approach of drawing up manuals [2].

For this reason, the development of a language course should take into account such aspects as – atomic supply of material (suggest to the user with

new information in a sufficient volume that does not violate his usual way of life, but do not overload him, otherwise he will switch attention to materials that require less load), gamification and socialization (the ability to play with other users, as well as to make all sorts of interactions with them, increases the interest of the younger generation, universal availability (that will allow the user to effortlessly access the material) and relevance (the material must meet the modern interests of native speakers – IT terminology, current jargon, phrases that are currently in use) [3-4].

Among the most important criteria that require consideration when designing a foreign language course, should be considered such as target audience selection, the separation into lessons and topics subject to the interests of the students of the course, the choice of format of the tasks based on the direction and application of the material being studied, for example, development of the vocal apparatus or the teaching of reading in the selected language.

Target audience selection

First of all, when developing a language course, it is necessary to take into account for whom this language course is intended. Age category, race, gender, nationality, and other characteristics may have a certain impact on what material will be assimilated. A person familiar with the Spanish language will understand what "Siesta" is, and a person who speaks Russian will not hesitate to answer what "jurodivyi" is. A similar example can be given in relation to age-children are better at learning colours, new words and phenomena, while adults are better at remembering information presented in a structured text form, which does not exclude the possibility of developing associative memory based on images.

Online English school Skyeng conducted a study that found that children are better at learning material presented in the form of images, adults - if the material is presented in the form of text. Besides, children were characterized by an interest in engaging in dialogues with teachers, while adults are comfortable format is the format of audio lessons. According to the way information is consumed, children are interested in colourful videos, while adults prefer text blogs [5].

In addition, taking into account generally accepted assessments of language proficiency (for example, CEFR - Common European Framework of Reference [6]), the target audience can be aimed at both superficial study of the basics of the language, and deep learning of the language, for example, with the correct accent.

Accordingly, this should influence the content of the developed language course with the choice of a suitable set of words (for example, a set

of words for spoken English, Business English, English for Travelers), examples, audio and graphic materials.

The division into lessons and topics

When developing a language course, it is also worth paying special attention to how the material for the student will be divided. A typical example of division into lessons and topics involves separation and successive immersion in the language, starting with the study of the alphabet and the basics of grammar, continuing with lessons that allow you to say Hello and introduce yourself, ending with lessons that allow you to Express some thought expressed by complex language forms.

However, if a potential student already has some experience in the chosen language, he may be interested in a different level of material, for example, business courses in English or Latin for scientists. This should be taken into account, as the student may refuse to take the course if the level of material and subject matter will either not match the level of the student (too difficult or too easy), or be out of the student's area of interest.

Determining how the material is fed

The next important factor is to determine the method of presentation of the material-video lectures, lectures in the format of chat or the format of "question-answer", graphic material, material in the form of notes or tables. This item is closely related to the choice of the target audience and the division into topics, as it affects the intellectual and cultural level of students. Within each group of the selected target audience, it is necessary to take into account age, cultural and regional characteristics. As an example, if the course is aimed at pre-school children or primary school students, the course should include a sufficient amount of material based on creating analogies and creating associations. In addition, gamification and characters familiar to students should be introduced to increase emotional response and develop associative memory. It should be borne in mind that this should be based on the cultural basis of the target audience-game characters should be known (for example, for Russian-speaking children's audience will be more understandable character Kolobok or Winnie the Pooh than the Japanese character Tororo).

Assessment of lesson results and student progress

To evaluate the effectiveness of training, you need to set special metrics that describe the effectiveness of the user's work. This can be an absolute or relative scale, expressed in abstract numerical values, describing, for example, the number of errors committed, or the number of completed tasks per unit of time.

However, for greater efficiency, it is also possible to use a dynamic relative scale that determines the progress of the student relative to the entire

group of students. This approach allows you to determine how an individual student is lagging behind or succeeding on a team scale.

The combination of absolute and relative metrics allows you to highlight the overall performance of the group, revealing gaps in knowledge that require study by the whole group, as well as difficulties in teaching individual students.

Modern online applications use a combination of relative and absolute metrics. This allows them to create dynamic curricula that are personalized for individual students. This personalization is made possible by the individual training of each user.

The choice of platform

It is also important to choose the appropriate platform on which to create a language course. This affects student accessibility, usability, and the breadth of available features. Compact courses, for which it is possible to simplify the lessons to the size of small tests and quizzes, can be implemented in mobile applications that can be available to the user always and everywhere. At the same time, complex academic courses can be implemented in a desktop format, allowing the user, for example, to view video lectures and perform large tests based on, for example, large texts, which for greater accessibility recommend the use of monitors instead of small mobile phone screens.

On the other hand, it is possible to combine platforms, allowing the user to move in the study of the material as it is convenient for him -- on the road on a mobile phone, and in the office or at home from a personal computer.

The advantages of the mobile platform include the availability of peripherals such as a camera and microphone, as well as compactness, while personal computers offer a large working space and affordable computing power.

On the other hand, online learning can go beyond the application of mobile applications, moving to offline mode. In this case, it is assumed that the user can participate in the training through the application, receiving some of the training material through live communication with the teacher. This approach may be the best option for foreign language schools that teach their students live, through working in the classroom.

Results of a study of the material taking into account the needs of students

Personalization and deep elaboration of content taking into account the needs of users allowed to improve the memorization of the material, and gamification increases the interest and involvement of the user.

Within the framework of Busuu and Duolingo applications, academic research was conducted, which showed the following positive results: more

than 84% of users improved their writing skills, and the learning speed increased by 1.5 times compared to traditional methods. Two months of learning through apps allowed 75% of users to improve their speaking skills, 22 hours of using the app were equivalent to one semester of language learning at the University, and students who had never previously encountered the language studied showed results comparable to students who have some experience of language learning [7-8].

At the moment, the active audience of such applications exceeds several tens of millions of users, which signals a wide interest in learning foreign languages and searching for alternative methods of learning, other than the classical memorization of words and performing tasks on textbooks. The ability to use applications in education allows you to expand the availability of education as such, since the student is able to study the material in which he is personally interested, at any time and in any place.

As part of the study of the topic, it is possible to further study the topic and develop their own algorithms for evaluating the material and repeating the lessons learned. Based on a wide range of existing applications, it is possible to choose a unique way of presenting the material, not relying on standard methods, but using, for example, interaction with the outside world. By observing children who are just learning to talk, you can develop techniques that could find application among adult students.

Conclusion

Thus, the criteria mentioned above are decisive when creating a language course, allowing you to create material that meets certain criteria and needs with respect to the selected audience and the required level of training. In the next step to increase the quality of both the educational material and method of its submission, will launch a major study of metrics allowing the personalized bar to measure the progress and to select material based on the needs and capabilities of students.

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THE EFFECT OF PARTICLE SIZE AND MORPHOLOGY ON THE SINTER ABILITY OF FE-CU-SN-NI COMPOSITES MADE BY POWDER METALURGY

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